

SOCIO-CULTURAL SPACE OF BUTH JO DARO SITE WITHIN INDUS CIVILIZATION

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Abstract

This research paper has been extracted from the PhD thesis of author on Buth jo Daro an Indus period site located in lower Sindh .Buth jo Daro site is situated at taluka Manjhand of district Jamshoro,65 km away from district headquarter on Indus Highway, the site was accidentally discovered through digging a wider and deeper drain popularly known as RBOD throughout the site area, millions of cultural objects were dumped in multiple heaps, author has made surface analysis to identify the period and important archaeological artifacts laying on surface of the site.stretigic location of Buth jo daro site make it junction for trade, starting from its own vicinity to Amri, Mohen jo daro and stretching up to Baluchistan, detailed analysis and comparison of craft activities at site and within Indus make it prominent as compared to other Indus period sites.

Key words: Buth jo Daro, Trade, Cultural Relations, lower Sindh, Indus Civilization.

INTRODUCTION

Sindh owes world famous heritage in lower Sindh regions, Buth jo Daro is one of heritage treasure located near the piedmonts of the Khirthar Range, it has been evidently seen that mountainous alluvial plain areas are extensively used for habitation. In Baluchistan and rest of Sindh further sites like Amri, Kot Diji and Mehargarh belongs to Early Indus period. Buth jo Daro having special location it benefits from two distinct geographical zones: The steep slopes and, on the other hand the alluvial plain for crop farming and Agrarian production respectively of the pastoralist & herders. Seasonal rains transform the Khirthar Range (literally meaning "cream of milk") into a lush green vegetative areas that attracts most of nomadic communities along with their herds for grazing and temporary settlements, herds primarily consisting of goats and sheep.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Author has made multiple field visits to site, surveyed thoroughly, flagged the concentrated areas of artifacts, photographed, surface collections, artifacts classifications and catalogued for proper documentation and understanding, data collection was made through primary and secondary sources.

Main Text

Accidental discovery of Buth jo daro site has marked a major discovery in the field of south Asian archaeology, the Buth jo Daro site came to an attention in 2017, but it was priory dug much before through the heavy machinery for constructing a drain called RBOD (Right Bank Outfall Drain) a project of government for draining chemical waste. The site being located in surroundings of piedmont area of the Khirthar mountain ranges which stand in west, bordering Sindh and Baluchistan. Heavy rain floods during monsoon seasons adding minerals for fertile agreeculturing same it cause silt depositions on plain areas so for the site of Buth jo Daro was buried deep inside whose cultural artifacts were surfaced through deep digging by machines.

The site is more than 5 hectares in area with dozens of high mounds caused by digging of RBOD, heaps containing scattered, mixed cultural artifacts, due to heap deposition. Surface contains the artifacts majorly belonging to Early Indus Period (3400 BC), Mature Indus period (2400 BC) and some artifacts of late and post Indus period.

Interaction of Major Indus cities and towns (source: Harrapa.com)

Fig No.01, Mound view of the site, Source: Author

Trade: having specialized geographical location on the bank of river Indus and Khirthar Mountains in west make this site transitional up to Baluchistan. Being on bank of river Indus Both jo Daro managed both transit routes through land and waters, Amri the contemporary site to Buth jo daro is only 39 km away on same river Indus, Chanhu Daro a important Indus site famous for semi-precious bead, metal, shell and steatite making center is also on same river just same direct distance as the Amri has, Mohen the Daro the center of Indus Civilization is just 250 km away from Buth Jo Daro on same river which further consolidate the idea of trade between Buth jo Daro and rest of Indus sites,

Fig No.02- RBOD is passing through the Site, Source: Author

Fig No.03 Indus highway passing by the site, Source: Author

Findings: Discovery of Semi-precious stones like Barrel bead of Lapis lazuli and Carnelian pendant, disk bead, copper chisels, copper fragments, bull figurines, bullock carts, perforated, plain, painted, Buff ware, fish scale pottery, Terracotta cakes and bangles, Long blades, aero heads, kiln slags, brunt bricks, broken shell bangles, T.C balls and Stone weights are considered the major findings of Buth jo Daro. The presence of variety artifacts can only be possible through due to extensive trade made with around and faraway sites. Specialized weight system found at Buth jo Daro proves activity of internal and external trade.

Fig No.04 Carnelian & Lapis lazuli found at Buth jo Daro: Source Author Fig No.05

The presence of Indus seals in Mesopotamia and Elam is much enough to establish the trade connection between two great civilizations during third millennium BC, Mr. Gadd and Professor Langdon has described the details of seals very comprehensively. Furthermore the pottery presence and trefoil design on statue at Al Ubaid further consolidate the idea of having trade and cultural relations (John Marshall pp-103). In Fig No.05 the carnelian barrel bead is found from the site of Buth jo Daro which clearly resemblance with beads found from the ancient Mesopotamia shown in Fig No 06, This great deal of resemblances witnesses the mutual trade did not limited only to Mohen jo Daro but up to its other towns including Buth jo Daro. Carnelian has been remained the important Jewell of Indus jewelry hoards, the carnelian was brought to Indus from Gujrat India and the regions of Hindu Kush, red captivating color and lines made this gemstone more demanding ornamental stone in Indus Civilization. Indus ornaments has variety from clay bangle to ivory and shell bangles from semi-precious to precious stones with reflects the sustainable economy and symmetrical wearing.

Fig No.06, Lapis lazuli beads from Mesopotamia, (google. Image.) Fig No.07 Shell artifacts, Source: Author

Shell and ivory has been remained status symbols throughout ancient to modern societies, rare viability of ivory at Indus makes it to understand that exuberance depiction of elephants on Indus seals make this animal important socially and religiously, but shell a white variety in exuberance at Indus but due to its brittle composition was difficult to work and to shape it hence it was abundant availability to its craftsmen. The craftsmen of Sumerians and Babylonians were expert enough to make shell statues. Srilanka, Indian Madras and Calcutta were the famous shell producing centers,

fascioloria trapezium a type of shell was documented by Colonel Sewell, turbinella pyrum has been recorded. Sank shell had been frequently under use of Sumerians (EJH Mackay pp 563-64)
the variety of shell artifacts has been discovered from the site of Buth Jo Daro (Shown in Fig No.07) includes the small conch shells and bangles and wrist bands made of fine white shell made with careful sophisticated Indus technology, this complex expertise of shell making ornaments along with semiprecious stones make the craftsmen of Buth jo Daro next level to Mohen jo Daro.

Fig No.08 Kot Dijjan with dark red band and Buff ware-Fig No.09 dish on stand bottom of plate

Fig No.10 Drawings of Jar miniature-Fig No.11 .figurine of bull toy, Source: Author

Fig No.12 Jar Miniature. Source: Author.

Fig No. 13 Fish Scale pattern

Presence of buff ware pottery of Baluchistan at Amri and Buth jo Daro shows close trade and cultural relations maintained during Indus periods throughout Indus simultaneously, particularly the fish scale potsherds of Kot Diji brings Kot Diji in line with Amri, Baluchistan and Buth jo Daro together.

Fig No.14 Source: Khan.1965, Google.com- Fig No.15 Ribbed Potsherds, Source: Author

Ribbed pottery:

In contrast the ribbed pottery examples are not much but fewer ,ribs around th shoulders of pot are raised with round base (Marshall pp-300). Same ribbed pottery has been discovered from the site of both jo daro, same scarcity of ribbed pottery at Buth jo Daro like Mohen jo Daro arises the the questions that why the ribbed pottery sherds are fewer in number, alike Mohen jo Daro the presencec of ribbed pottery makes Buth jo Daro site much signified and dignified.

Statistical details of artifacts found at Buth jo Daro

CONCLUSION:

Buth jo Daro site has special strategic location at Khirthar piedmont area which enabled his lands fertile and prairies for animal grazing, being established at bank of Indus river the site maintained socio economic relations with neighboring sites like Amri, Chanhu Daro, Mohen jo Daro, Kot Diji and other Indus period sites in Dadu district. Pottery sherds (Plain, Painted, Perforated, Buff, fine ware, Coarse ware, averted and inverted rims pottery) Stone blades Stone weights, Semi-precious stone, Sand stone, Copper Chisel ,Disk Bead, Jar Miniature ,Complete & broken TC Cakes ,T.C Bangles Bullock miniature, Bullock cart frame ,Brunt Bricks and Shell pieces. Complex craft technologies has been contributing to economy of Buth Jo Daro, this river port site might have been well organized town site, as plenty of complete and brunt bricks surfaces the site, for understanding proper layout of town planning extensive excavation is necessary to make.

All this proves undoubtedly that Buth jo Daro site has two major periods occupations Early and Mature Indus period (3400-2600 BC) with fewer artifacts belongs to late and post Indus period. Availability of semi-precious stones at Buth jo Daro confirms the trade relation locally and up to other civilizations, the presence of imported artifacts can be possible through the direct trade with other civilization or trade with Mohen jo Daro and then items were sold or redistributed to other Indus period sites.

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